

ФУНДАМЕНТАЛ ТАДҚИҚОТЛАР ЖУРНАЛИ

ЖУРНАЛ ФУНДАМЕНТАЛЬНЫХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ | JOURNAL OF FUNDAMENTAL STUDIES

MUSAEVA Nasibakhon

*ISFT Institute in Tashkent, Uzbekistan,
Accounting Department*

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BUSINESS PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS

ANNOTATION

A key instrument for assessing a company's financial performance and stability, financial accounting analysis forms the basis of strategic decision-making. The balance sheet, income statement, and cash flow statement are the three main financial statements that are thoroughly examined as part of this analytical process, which provides information about the entity's profitability, liquidity management, and overall financial health. By employing techniques such as financial ratio analysis, trend analysis, and industry benchmarking, analysts assess key financial aspects, including liquidity, solvency, operational efficiency, and profitability.

A professional Business Performance Analysis is aimed to provide along with dashboard of past financial statements of one of the Pharmacy entities in Uzbekistan in 2022-2023, to visualizes the financial health and performance metrics of the company, particularly in managing costs and improving profitability in months where losses are indicated. Specifically, ratio calculation to identify the business performance and operational efficiency over the year, guiding decisions in management and investment targeted.

Key words: Management Accounting, dashboard, risk management, stakeholders, ratio calculations, financial ratios, profitability ratios, liquidity ratios, solvency ratios, efficiency ratio, Gross profit margin, Net profit margin, Current ratio, Quick ratio, Debt-to-equity ratio, Inventory turnover, Total asset turnover, Return on equity (ROE), Return on assets (ROA), The return days from trade receivables, The creditors turnover days ratio, Expense ratio, The return on trade receivable ratio, The return days from trade receivables

БИЗНЕС САМАРАДОРЛИГИНИ ТАҲЛИЛ ҚИЛИШ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Компаниянинг молиявий фаолияти ва барқарорлигини баҳолашнинг асосий воситаси, молиявий бухгалтерия таҳлили стратегик қарорлар қабул қилишнинг асосини ташкил етади. Баланс, даромадлар тўғрисидаги ҳисобот ва пул оқимлари тўғрисидаги ҳисобот ушбу таҳлилий жараённинг бир қисми сифатида тўлиқ кўриб чиқиладиган учта асосий молиявий ҳисобот бўлиб, у корхонанинг рентабеллиги, ликвидлигини бошқариш ва умумий молиявий ҳолати тўғрисида маълумот беради. Молиявий нисбатларни таҳлил қилиш, тенденцияларни таҳлил қилиш ва саноатни таққослаш каби усуллардан фойдаланган ҳолда, таҳлилчилар ликвидлик, тўлов қобилияти, операцион самарадорлик ва рентабелликни ўз ичига олган асосий молиявий жиҳатларни баҳолайдилар.

Бизнес самарадорлигини professional таҳлил қилиш Ўзбекистондаги дорихона корхоналаридан бирининг 2022-2023 йилларда ўтган молиявий ҳисоботларини бошқариш панели билан бир қаторда компаниянинг молиявий саломатлиги ва ишлаш кўрсаткичларини, хусусан харажатларни бошқариш ва йўқотишлар кўрсатилган ойларда рентабелликни оширишга қаратилган. Хусусан, нисбати ҳисоблаш мақсадли бошқариш ва инвестиция қарорлар ҳидоят, йил давомида иш фаолиятини ва операцион самарадорлигини аниқлаш.

Калит сўзлар: бошқарув ҳисоби, бошқарув панели, рискларни бошқариш, манфаатдор томонлар, нисбатлар ҳисоб-китоблари, молиявий коэффициентлар, рентабеллик коэффициентлари, ликвидлик коэффициентлари, тўлов қобилияти коэффициентлари, самарадорлик коэффициенти, ялпи фойда маржаси, соф фойда маржаси, жорий нисбат, тезкор нисбат, қарз-капитал нисбати, инвентаризация айланмаси, жами активлар айланмаси, қайтиш капитал (ROE), активларнинг рентабеллиги (ROA), савдо дебиторлик қарзларидан қайтиш кунлари, кредиторлар айланмаси кунларининг нисбати, харажатлар нисбати, савдо дебиторлик қарзларининг қайтарилиши, савдо дебиторлик қарзларидан қайтиш кунлари.

АНАЛИЗ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ БИЗНЕСА

АННОТАЦИЯ

Анализ финансового учета, являющийся ключевым инструментом оценки финансовых показателей и стабильности компании, является основой для принятия стратегических решений. Бухгалтерский баланс, отчет о прибылях и убытках и отчет о движении денежных средств являются тремя основными финансовыми отчетами, которые тщательно анализируются в рамках этого аналитического процесса, который предоставляет информацию о прибыльности предприятия, управлении ликвидностью и общем финансовом состоянии. Используя такие методы, как анализ финансовых коэффициентов, анализ тенденций и отраслевой бенчмаркинг, аналитики оценивают ключевые финансовые аспекты, включая ликвидность, платежеспособность, операционную эффективность и прибыльность.

Профессиональный анализ эффективности бизнеса направлен на то, чтобы, наряду с информационной панелью прошлых финансовых отчетов одного из аптечных предприятий Узбекистана за 2022-2023 годы, наглядно представить финансовое состояние и показатели эффективности компании, особенно в области управления затратами и повышения прибыльности в месяцы, когда отмечаются убытки. В частности, расчет коэффициента позволяет определить эффективность бизнеса и операционной деятельности в течение года, ориентируясь на принятие управленческих решений и целевые инвестиции.

Ключевые слова: Управленческий учет, информационная панель, управление рисками, заинтересованные стороны, расчеты коэффициентов, финансовые коэффициенты, коэффициенты рентабельности, коэффициенты ликвидности, коэффициенты платежеспособности, коэффициент эффективности, маржа валовой прибыли, маржа чистой прибыли, Коэффициент текущей ликвидности, коэффициент быстрой ликвидности, соотношение долга к собственному капиталу, оборачиваемость запасов, Общая оборачиваемость активов, Доходность на собственный капитал (ROE), Рентабельность активов (ROA), Количество дней возврата торговой дебиторской задолженности, Коэффициент оборачиваемости средств кредиторами, Коэффициент расходов, Коэффициент возврата торговой дебиторской задолженности, Количество дней возврата торговой дебиторской задолженности.

Introduction

Increasingly the demand for both Management Accountant is significant and continues to grow across various industries. Because they serve as a key tool to flourish the business in competitive market. For example, in management accounting - using ratio analysis play active role in financial decision-making.

Businesses of all sizes require professionals who can interpret financial data and ratios to make informed decisions about investments, resource allocation, and strategic planning. Also, investor relations can be analyzed with the help of ratio calculations. Publicly traded companies need professionals who can analyze financial ratios to communicate effectively with investors and stakeholders about the company's financial performance and prospects. Moreover, Risk Management is identified through the topic under scrutiny. Companies need experts who can assess financial risks and vulnerabilities through ratio analysis to develop strategies for mitigating these risks and ensuring financial stability.

Literature review

Financial ratios are quantitative measures derived from financial statement items to assess a company's financial condition, performance, and stability. They can be classified into several categories: liquidity ratios, solvency ratios, profitability ratios, and efficiency ratios. (Brigham, E. F., & Ehrhardt, M. C.). Foundational knowledge on financial ratio analysis can be gained from this textbook.

Profitability ratios measure a company's ability to generate earnings relative to its revenue, assets, and equity. Key ratios include Gross Margin, Operating Margin, Return on Assets (ROA), and Return on Equity (ROE). Applicable for Analysis of trends in profitability and comparison with industry benchmarks. This source offers a deep dive into profitability ratios and their significance for stakeholders. (Gitman, L. J., & Zutter, C. J. (2012).

Liquidity ratios, such as the Current Ratio and Quick Ratio, assess a company's ability to meet short-term obligations. These metrics are crucial for evaluating the risk of financial distress. The result of calculation can be used to monitor cash flow positions and to ensure financial flexibility. Reading the textbook, one can go insight into examples of liquidity management and its implications for business sustainability (Ross, S. A., Westerfield, R., & Jordan, B. D. (2010). Fundamentals of Corporate Finance).

Solvency ratios, like Debt-to-Equity and Interest Coverage Ratio, are used to assess a company's ability to sustain operations indefinitely by examining its debt levels relative to its assets or equity. These ratios are particularly useful in the context of long-term financial planning and risk assessment. This comprehensive guide offers insight into the use of solvency ratios in corporate finance (Brealey, R. A., Myers).

Efficiency ratios (also known as activity ratios) such as Inventory Turnover and Receivables Turnover measure how effectively a company uses its assets. This is useful for assessing operational performance and resource utilization. This book covers various techniques to enhance organizational efficiency through ratio analysis by Horngren, C. T., Sundem.

Using ratios to compare a company's **financial metrics** against industry norms or direct competitors. Koller, T., Goedhart, M., & Wessels, D. (2010). Taking the practice one can measure and managing the value of companies. This reference gives methods for using financial ratios in valuation and strategic management.

Penman, S. H. (2010) mentions that ratios can be influenced by accounting policies and may not reflect current market conditions. In fact, empirical studies often discuss the limitations and potential biases in ratio analysis, suggesting complementary tools and techniques. In Financial Statement Analysis and Security Valuation textbook he critiques traditional financial analysis methods and suggests robust approaches.

Research methodology

The systematic approach and techniques used to conduct research and gather data. It serves as a roadmap for how the research was carried out, allowing readers to understand the reliability and validity of the study's findings.

Both qualitative and quantitative methods are utilized in the project because there are certain data to be calculated through financial ratios which are invaluable tools for comprehending the figures laid out in financial statements and assessing the overall financial well-being of a company. These ratios span various categories, including profitability, liquidity, solvency, efficiency, and valuation.

Key financial ratios to be acquainted with encompass:

- ⇒ **Gross profit margin** indicates the percentage of profit generated by the company after deducting direct cost of sales from revenue. The formula for calculating the gross profit margin is:

$$\text{Gross Profit Margin (\%)} = \left(\frac{\text{Revenue} - \text{Cost of Goods Sold}}{\text{Revenue}} \right) \times 100$$

- ⇒ **Net profit margin** reflects the percentage of profit generated by the company after deducting all expenses, including interest and tax, from revenue. The formula for calculating the net profit margin is:

$$\text{Net Profit Margin (\%)} = \left(\frac{\text{Net Profit}}{\text{Revenue}} \right) \times 100$$

- ⇒ **Current ratio** measures the company's ability to meet short-term liabilities within a year. The formula for the current ratio is:

$$\text{Current Ratio} = \frac{\text{Current Assets}}{\text{Current Liabilities}}$$

- ⇒ **Quick ratio** assesses the company's ability to settle short-term liabilities within a year using highly liquid assets exclusively. The formula for the quick ratio is:

$$\text{Quick Ratio} = \frac{\text{Current Assets} - \text{Inventory}}{\text{Current Liabilities}}$$

- ⇒ **Debt-to-equity ratio** indicates the proportion of debt to equity utilized by the company for financing. The formula for the debt-to-equity ratio is:

$$\text{Debt-to-Equity Ratio} = \frac{\text{Total Debt}}{\text{Total Equity}}$$

- ⇒ **Inventory turnover** measures how frequently the entire inventory is sold within a specific period. The formula for the inventory turnover is:

$$\text{Inventory Turnover} = \frac{\text{Cost of Goods Sold (COGS)}}{\text{Average Inventory}}$$

⇒ **Total asset turnover** assesses the efficiency with which the company generates revenue from its total assets. The formula for the total asset turnover is:

$$\text{Total Asset Turnover} = \frac{\text{Net Sales}}{\text{Average Total Assets}}$$

⇒ **Return on equity (ROE)** gauges the company's ability to generate profit using equity investments. The formula for the ROE is:

$$\text{Return on Equity (ROE)} = \frac{\text{Net Income}}{\text{Average Shareholders' Equity}}$$

⇒ **Return on assets (ROA)** reflects the company's proficiency in managing and utilizing its assets to generate profit. The formula for ROA is:

$$\text{Return on Assets (ROA)} = \frac{\text{Net Income}}{\text{Average Total Assets}}$$

⇒ **The return days from trade receivables** also known as the collection period, measures the average number of days it takes for a company to collect payments from its customers on credit sales. It's calculated as follows:

$$\text{Return Days from Trade Receivables} = \frac{\text{Average Accounts Receivable}}{\text{Net Credit Sales}} \times 365$$

⇒ **The creditors turnover days ratio** measures the average number of days it takes for a company to pay its suppliers. It's calculated as follows:

$$\text{Return Days from Trade Payables} = \frac{\text{Average Accounts Payable}}{\text{Average Daily Credit Purchases}} \times 365$$

⇒ **Expense ratio** is used to assess the efficiency of cost management or to compare expenses relative to revenue. Here's the formula:

$$\text{Expense Ratio (as a percentage)} = \left(\frac{\text{Total Expenses}}{\text{Total Revenue}} \right) \times 100\%$$

⇒ **The return on trade receivable ratio** measures the return a company earns on its trade receivables (customers). It's calculated as follows:

$$\text{ROTR Ratio} = \frac{\text{Net Income}}{\text{Average Accounts Receivable}}$$

⇒ **The return days from trade receivables**, also known as the collection period, measures the average number of days it takes for a company to collect payments from its customers on credit sales. It's calculated as follows:

$$\text{ROTP Ratio} = \frac{\text{Net Income}}{\text{Average Accounts Payable}}$$

Dashboard description

Dashboard is a visual representation of data, designed to provide users with a quick and comprehensive view of key performance indicators (KPIs), metrics, and trends within an organization or system. They serve the purpose of facilitating data-driven decision-making by presenting information in a clear, concise, and easily understandable format.

Dashboard: Monitoring Business Performance of the entity in 2022-2023

The Dashboard displays a detailed financial performance of the company for the years 2022 and 2023, focusing on various critical financial metrics. Each panel is displayed within the dashboard to provide insights into different aspects of the company's financial health and operational efficiency.

To start with **Net Profit Margin**, a reduction from 10.31% in 2022 to 8.53% in 2023 indicates a decrease in profitability, which could result from increased costs or decreased revenue efficiency. Likewise, index of **Gross Profit Margin** saw a slight decrease from 22.98% in 2022 to 20.15% in 2023 suggesting that the cost of goods sold as a percentage of sales has increased, impacting the overall profitability.

By contrast, **Total Expense Ratio** shows an increase from 8.5% in 2022 to 11.1% in 2023. This indicates bad control over expenses or a rise in operational costs relative to total revenue. Unlike this, trend of **Current Ratio** decreased dramatically from 6.0 in 2022 to 2.1 in 2023 where a significant drop suggests a reduction in the company's liquidity, potentially indicating tighter cash flow or higher short-term liabilities. Meanwhile, **Debt-to-Equity** increased sharply from 19.92% to 89.16% meaning a substantial increase in debt used to finance the company's assets relative to equity, indicating higher financial leverage and potential risk.

Like **Inventory Turnover** decreased from 8.0 in 2022 to 4.9 in 2023, the **Asset Turnover** also experienced a decline from 8.9 in 2022 to 4.9 in 2023. These falls suggest lower efficiency in managing inventory and assets to generate sales.

A lower **ROP** suggests that the company is using less credit from suppliers or perhaps improving its cash position to negotiate better terms, which could be favorable in maintaining good supplier relationships but might also indicate less efficient use of financial leverage. However, a stability in **ROR** is beneficial, as it indicates that the company does not face increased difficulty in collecting from its customers, which is crucial for maintaining cash flow. Understanding these specific functions within the broader financial context is to better analyze the company's operational efficiency and financial strategy, particularly in managing its working capital components-payables and receivables-which are crucial for short-term financial health.

Return on Assets (ROA) saw a downward trend from 51.61% in 2022 to 42.05% in 2023, parallely **Return on Equity (ROE)** dropped from 79.54% in 2022 to 42.05% in 2023. Both reductions reflect declining effectiveness in utilizing the company's assets and equity to produce profits.

Discussion

In the Dashboard a series of challenges faced by the company from 2022 to 2023 illustrated, that is marked by reduced efficiency in asset and inventory management, increased financial leverage, and decreased profitability and liquidity. The changes in these key financial indicators signal a need for strategic adjustments in operations, financial management, and perhaps cost control measures to improve financial health and reduce vulnerability due to high debt levels. By this information, Stakeholders, who need to consider these insights critical for making informed decisions regarding future investments, operational strategies, and financial management practices.

Conclusion

The company underwent several challenges and areas of concern that necessitate immediate attention and strategic adjustments. Operational efficiencies also appear to have weakened, as evidenced by decreased inventory and asset turnover rates, which could impact the company's cash flow and operational agility. The current ratio's sharp decline highlights potential liquidity issues, pointing towards a need for better cash management practices to ensure that the company can meet its short-term obligations.

While there are indications of improved expense management, the overall financial health of the company is precarious unfortunately. To navigate these challenges, it is critical for the company to implement rigorous financial controls, reassess its operational strategies, and possibly diversify its revenue streams to stabilize its financial position and foster sustainable growth. Immediate action in these areas will be crucial to reversing the negative trends and setting a foundation for future stability and profitability.

Recommendations

Based on the comprehensive financial performance dashboards provided for the entity from 2022 to 2023, several recommendations suggested to enhance the company's financial health and operational efficiency. For instance, by Optimization on Cost Management. Notably high cost of sales relative to revenue suggests a need to streamline production processes or negotiate better terms with suppliers to enhance gross margins.

Also, analyzing administrative expenses, particularly those showing significant variance through the months, and identifying areas for cost reduction without compromising operational integrity is a real concern. In addition, the company should stabilize Revenue Fluctuations by exploring strategies to stabilize revenue fluctuations seen throughout the year. This might involve diversifying product lines, enhancing marketing efforts, or entering new markets. Despite a decrease in overall revenue, efforts should be made to improve net and gross profit margins through cost optimization and pricing strategies.

The significant increase in debt-to-equity ratio is another urgent concern. The company should consider strategies to either reduce debt levels or enhance equity through retained earnings or equity financing to ensure financial stability and reduce interest cost burden. A proactive approach to managing liquidity should be adopted given the sharp decline in the current ratio. This includes better management of working capital, improving cash flows through quicker receivable turnovers, and better inventory management.

Given the constant tax rate impact, there is a room for improved tax planning strategies to ensure that the company maximizes its after-tax profitability. Close monitoring of financial operations such as finance costs and net foreign exchange gains or losses is crucial. The owner of the entity is suggested to consider leveraging financial hedging strategies to mitigate risks due to currency fluctuations. Likewise, there is a need to improve asset and inventory management to boost turnover rates, which helps in freeing up cash locked in slow-moving inventory and underutilized assets, thoroughly thought strategic review of the business plan and growth strategy is essential there. This should include an analysis of the market, competitive positioning, and innovation potential to regain growth momentum.

By implementing these recommendations, the entity can hope to address its current financial challenges, optimize operational performance, and set a robust foundation for sustainable growth and profitability in the coming years. Identifying the negative correlation of Gross profit and Net income is equally essential

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